

Does Foreign Direct Investment Boost Agribusiness? A Literature Review with Evidence from Developing Countries with a Focus on Nepal

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Abstract

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a critical catalyst for transforming agribusiness in developing economies through capital injection, technological diffusion, and improved market connectivity. Despite agriculture's central role in Nepal's economy, FDI inflows into the sector remain limited and inconsistent. This systematic review synthesizes evidence from studies published between 2000 and 2024 across databases such as ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and JSTOR to examine how FDI influences agribusiness performance globally, with a special focus on Nepal. Drawing upon Spillover Theory, Linkage Theory, and Dependency Theory, the review analyzes policy evolution, sectoral trends, and empirical experiences from countries including India, Vietnam, Bangladesh, and Mozambique. Findings indicate that while FDI can enhance productivity, strengthen value chains, and promote commercialization, its impact is highly dependent on regulatory clarity, institutional capacity, land governance, and the host country's absorptive ability. In Nepal, policy bottlenecks, land-use restrictions, weak coordination among government units, and inadequate monitoring have constrained potential benefits. Significant evidence gaps remain, particularly regarding project-level outcomes, environmental implications, and long-term developmental effects. The review concludes that maximizing FDI's contribution requires coherent policy reforms, enhanced institutional mechanisms, improved data systems, and targeted incentives for responsible and inclusive investment.

Keywords: *foreign direct investment, agribusiness development, developing countries, investment policy, technology transfer*